

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Drichta**FIRST NAME:** Jane**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Planning the Essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Benefits of The Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 5)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style and Turabian (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
7. Differences in U.K. English and U.S. English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING AT EUCLID UNIVERSITY

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been looking forward to starting this graduate program for a long time. I completed my MSc in Global Public Health and Policy in 2016 and have been working in the field over global health for almost 20 years. I have experience in both direct service delivery (I am trained as a midwife), and in operations, but wanted more of an academic framework from which to operate.

The first step in any new program is to become familiar with the format and style of the assigned papers, so I looked forward to beginning this class. Every program does things a little bit differently, so even though I am a native English speaker and have experience with graduate level writing, I began the class eagerly. Clear consistent communication is the basis not only for scholarship, but for success in business, or the non-governmental organization (NGO) world, in which I work.

In this essay I will explore the following key concepts: planning the essay itself, the dangers of plagiarism, the advantages of having and using a style guide, a quick review

of some English grammar concepts, the Chicago Manual of Style and Turabian citation system specifically, the process of producing the essay, and finally, some differences between UK and US English.

2) PLANNING THE ESSAY

Writing a coherent and cogent essay is one of the most important skills that a student can develop. It is something that reaches across all levels of scholarship, beginning in primary school, and continuing throughout any graduate education that a student may pursue. Its purpose is different from most other form of writing. Whereas an email or professional brief's function is to get information across as quickly as possible, an academic essay is to "persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1).

This distinction is important, as it is the way that scholarship advances. The student begins with an idea, develops their main position on said idea (the thesis) and then searches the literature to see what has already been written. They search for evidence that previous scholars have provided, as well as evidence to the contrary. The student then presents the evidence for both sides, interacting with the texts in a critical manner, and summarizing and synthesizing the main ideas of each piece of the literature. Only then can they see if their idea is viable, and fits into the work that has been done before by others. It is up to the reader then, to determine if enough evidence is provided to convince them that the student's viewpoint is correct.

I feel the most important step in writing an essay is this reading/searching for evidence. Without knowing what others have said on the subject, how can one be sure one's own ideas are original? The authors of the coursepack state unequivocally that spending time with the literature is essential, and that one cannot develop a strong thesis, not create an argument without this (EUCLID 2019, 2).

3) PLAGIARISM

Academic honesty is the basis upon which all scholarship rests. Without it, science cannot advance, never mind the fact that is completely unethical. However, it can be a bit confusing as to what constitutes this gravest of academic sins. Our course packet defines plagiarism as "when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2019, 5).

This is a good basic definition, but I was pleased to see that the authors went into more detail around specific examples. Straight out copying is straightforward enough, but things can get a little more confusing when it comes to paraphrasing. The coursepack states that the words must be different enough from the original that it cannot appear to have been lifted, and that the writing style cannot be similar (EUCLID 2019, 5). This is where plagiarism software really comes in handy, although of course there are limits to this. I was glad to see that we are required to use Grammarly for this. When I was teaching in a master's course, one of my students paraphrased poorly from Wikipedia. This was so

disheartening. If she had been required to show a plagiarism percentage, this could have been avoided, and she would not have been asked to leave the program. She insisted it was by accident, but of course we cannot know her true motivations.

This personal experience, as well as this assignment led me to investigate why students plagiarize, and how they justify their actions, leaving out those relatively rare cases of true accidental academic fraud). In study conducted at a mid-sized university in Spain, researcher found three main categories of student explanations (Comas-Forgas and Sureda-Negre 2010, 217). The first of these are student factors, meaning bad time management skills, procrastination, overloading themselves with too much work, etc. I would posit that this is probably the most common, as students, particularly adult learners, live very busy lives. It is always a challenge to complete assignments on time, and the temptation to cheat may be overwhelming if the consequences for late work are grave.

The second category is the ease with which students can now steal things from the internet (Comas-Forgas and Sureda-Negre 2010, 217). We literally have information at our fingertips, and it is much easier than it used to be to simply copy and paste. Sometimes the impulse to cut corners can be overwhelming, but if this were the norm, there would never be any new ideas. Science advances in small increments, building on what has come before. If this process is not respected, it will come to a standstill.

The third and final category is factors around course delivery, so characteristics of professors, their delivery, number of assignments, etc. (Comas-Forgas and Sureda-Negre 2010, 218). While some professors are undoubtedly better than others, I view this as a bit of an excuse. It is the student's responsibility to learn, and if the professor's style is making this difficult, then it is up to the student to open communication. It is no reason to plagiarize. This is a bad justification.

4) PRODUCING THE ESSAY

Our coursepack quite rightly says that the first step in writing the essay itself is to have a strong thesis (EUCLID 2019, 14). Without a firm thesis, which clearly states the point of view of the author, the essay will fall apart. After all, the thesis is the entire point of the essay; the rest of it exists to present evidence supporting the thesis, as well as to present critical points of view, to ensure a well-rounded paper.

While the introduction to the paper should move from the general to the specific, the coursepack makes the point that it is important to avoid large, inflated generalities, such as "Smith's contribution to the field of underwater basket weaving is incredible, the most important influence in the history of basketry (EUCLID 2019, 14). This is not only unlikely but gives the impression that the author has read every single source in the literature, and that they have the expertise to judge one as infinitely superior to all others. It destroys the trust in the author's scholarship, and simply looks silly.

The coursepack also entreats the student to vary their sentence structure and to avoid the passive voice (EUCLID 2019, 15). While the former is always good advice

(nobody wants to read a paper where all the sentences are the same length, or where the structure is always noun-verb-object; it makes for a boring essay) I was taught in my MSc. program that passive voice is acceptable for use in the sciences and social sciences. Curious, I went looking for confirmation of one or the other, and did find a source corroborating this and found that the University of New England in Australia agrees (UNE, n.d.). I will confirm that occasional passive voice is acceptable before using it in Euclid assignments.

5) THE ADVANTAGES OF A STYLE GUIDE

Consistent communication is made much easier if there is a set of rules to follow, with everyone in the same entity, be it a course, a business, or an industry using an identical set of regulations. For academic writing, this is most obvious in the realm of citation systems, although other factors such as language usage, formatting preferences, and fonts are also important.

Using a style guide also has several other advantages. I believe one of the most important is time management. If a student (or employee in the case of a workplace style guide) has a question regarding their writing, it is quick and easy to consult a style guide, rather than must track down a professor or a communications person for guidance. It is all right there in the guide.

Additionally, a style guide can be invaluable when there are multiple contributors to a written work, which is often the case in an academic setting. It would be odd to have three different authors using three different citation systems, for example, or if one used British spelling and another American. (Even if the style guide says that both are acceptable, such as at Euclid University, the author (s) still need to be consistent within a given document)

Susanah Noel, on her website Clariant Creative, goes one step further, saying that it makes the author consider every detail in a sentence (Noel 2016). Should any numerals be spelt out? Should the sentence end with a preposition? All these small details can be answered by a style guide, and by paying attention to these small details the writing is stronger.

6) LITERATURE REVIEW

When I first encountered this chapter in the coursepack, I thought it was going to be about a Literature Review, as in how to conduct a search of the literature in each subject, either for background and context, or to help prove or disprove a thesis. However, it became immediately obvious that this was about reviewing basic grammar rules, which is never a bad idea. Even though I am a native speaker, I sometimes still must pause and think about the difference between “its’ and “it’s,” or if a word ending in an “s” take an apostrophe only, or an apostrophe and an additional “s.” A review of the basics can never hurt.

I found rules two and three particularly interesting. Rule two states “use commas to bracket nonrestrictive phrases, which are not essential to the sentence's meaning (EUCLID 2019, 17). Rule three says “Do not use commas to bracket phrases that are essential to a sentence's meaning (EUCLID 2019, 17). I had never heard it phrased that way, nor indeed thought about it in this manner. I was taught that an appositive was a set of words that modify a noun, set off by commas. Dictionary.com agrees. They state that an appositive is an adjective or an adjective phrase that directly follows the noun it modifies (dictionary.com 2021). There is no mention of judgment around its importance.

However, the above may be seen to be splitting hairs. Many uses of commas in general are more of a personal stylistic measure than hard and fast grammar rules. The same can be said about the Oxford comma, that comma which is placed before the last in a series of items and recommended by our coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 19). I was interested to learn that many journalism style guides recommend omitting this comma (Pro Editing/Proofreading, n.d.) I will never give up the Oxford comma; they can pry it from my cold dead hands. I feel that it only adds clarity to a sentence and never reduces understanding of the author's intent.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE AND TURABIAN

Euclid University uses the Turabian system of citations. On page 25 of the coursepack, however, it clearly states “EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are fine (EUCLID 2019). This is confusing, and I was glad I had clarified that Turabian should be used exclusively, or I might have blithely gone on my merry way with Harvard, my favorite.

I feel this should be edited, as the information is no longer current. This is a criticism that I would level at a lot of the introductory literature at EUCLID. There is so much information that is outdated and this makes current standards difficult to identify. Another example of this exact topic is on the Help blog; it states that APA can be used for response papers, while Turabian is preferred for major papers. Upon clarifying with the instructor, I was told that this was from 2015 and is not the case anymore. Fair enough, but this is certainly not clear. In other parts of the university's website, it is stated that WHO and Oxford standards can also be used. This is clearly not the case.

I have not previously used Turabian, so I admit that I am a little nervous about learning a whole new style. I am very familiar with Modern Language Association (MLA), American Psychological Association (APA), and Harvard citations styles, but this one is new for me. I was relieved to see that there are many similarities between Turabian and the citations systems I have previously used, especially APA. The author-date format is similar, although there are slight punctuation differences. I have not used footnotes, as required in the major paper, since 1987 in high school. The previous styles I have used a Reference List at the end of major essays as well, but I will deal with that when the time comes.

8) DIFFERENCES IN UK AND US ENGLISH

My entire life has been a mish mash of UK and US traditions and customs, including spellings, idioms, cultural references, and more. Born in Yorkshire, UK, my family moved to the U/S when I was 14, the only members of our extended family to emigrate. I attended undergraduate university in the US but did my post graduate studies in London and Liverpool. As an adult, my time has been split almost evenly between the two, when not living in various other countries for work. Additionally, when in the U.S, I live in the city of Seattle, which is very close the Canadian border, so there are Canadian influences as well. Right now, I live in Haiti, where written English is mostly SAE. With such a varied background, I have had to learn to code switch between the two types of written and spoken English for almost my entire life.

Most universities have a policy of using either Standard British English (SBE) or Standard American English (SAE) depending on their home countries' styles. However, EUCLID's style rules allow for both types, which to me is very fitting for a truly international university (my postgraduate alma mater, Queen Mary University of London did the same, as there were an abundance of international students in my course). It is, however, important to be consistent in one's chosen style, whichever that may be. Canada, it should be noted, uses a mixture of both SBE and SAE, so it can become a bit confusing.

Most people are aware of the common differences in spellings, "o" vs "ou" as in "color/colour, or "s" vs "c" as in "offense/offence. However, the coursepack does detail some of the more uncommon differences, especially those where the entire word is spelt differently, such as check/cheque or jail/goal (EUCLID 2019, 28). I really think most Americans are not even aware of these differences, and honestly, after so many years, I am sometimes not even sure which spelling goes with which country (this sometimes happens when I am driving too, when I am the only one on a road; luckily, it has not resulted in an accident yet!).

The coursepack also mentions words that are spelt the same, but pronounced differently, specifically mentioning the word "dance" as an example (EUCLID 2019, 27). I am assuming that the writer of the coursepack is thinking that all Americans use the short "a" sound, and that all British people use the "ah" pronunciation. However, this is untrue, and so this might be confusing for non-native speakers. In the north of England, Yorkshire, where I am from, we use the short a sound (Gaidamavičiūtė, n.d.).

It is considered a lower-class accent; like most things in the U.K., it can be brought back to the class divide. Dialects like mine are often "trained out" of children at school if their parents wish them to advance in the world. Like previously mentioned, I code switch often between SBE and SAE. However, I also find that I code switch between upper- and lower-class English accents, lower when I am back in Yorkshire, and upper when I am around other British people, especially abroad. (There can be an entire other essay written about how British ex-pats tend to be more British than those at home!)

9) CONCLUSION

This was a very helpful introduction to academic writing at Euclid. There were some issues with clarity and I still anticipate a period of adjustment when it come to the Turabian, but overall, it was a useful experience. The professor I have worked with so far has been very responsive to emails and questions, so I feel like relying on the faculty for questions is welcomed at Euclid.

This was quite a meta-assignment, if you will, writing about writing. But I shall bear the pertinent points in mind as I move through the course. Planning the essay is the first step, and it will always be important to be mindful of plagiarism, even that which is inadvertently. In producing the essay, itself, I will use all the rules of English grammar, and if I am unsure, I will be able to research the answer using the style guide, the Chicago Manual of Style, while using the Turabian citing system to recognize my sources. I will also keep to one style of English.

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